

CHANGING ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract

Purpose - Organizational culture is based on beliefs, values and behaviors considered appropriate by its members. This can cause employees to leave the organization or stimulate them to behave in a certain way. This paper aims to analyze if and how the organizational culture in pre-university education institutions could be changed.

Methodology/approach - For comprehensive understanding of this concept, a literature review will be conducted based on various studies, books and specialist articles.

Findings - The study will focus on identifying factors influencing school organizational culture and presenting a model for change.

Research limitations/implications – The limitation of the present research derives from the complexity of the addressed topic. The present paper provides an overview of literature review, however an interesting future research direction could be the analysis of school organizational cultures by school level. It would be equally useful to analyze and compare the organizational cultures in the rural environment with those in the urban environment.

Practical implications – This paper presents the factors that influence the culture of a pre-university educational institution and identifies a model of culture change in schools.

Originality/value – The originality of this work consists in following the process of changing the school organizational culture from the influencing factors to a concrete model of change.

Key words: organizational culture, pre-university educational institutions.

Introduction

Whether we like it or not, we are all born into a certain culture, we develop and place ourselves in a certain cultural horizon, and we are all both creators and receivers of culture at the same time. Culture mirrors things and represents, at the same time, a frame through which the world is viewed. In depth, it reproduces the reality of those in social organizations, providing support, identity and creating a framework conducive to occupational learning. Each pre-university educational institution (school) presents a different reality or even a different mentality of school life, which is most often expressed as "the way we do things around here" [Deal and Peterson, 2016].

In specialized literature, there is no consensus regarding the definition of organizational culture. However, it emerges that the organizational culture represents an important subsystem of the institution and is a factor that dictates the organizational effectiveness and the level of

quality of the professional life of its members. Several approaches have led to correct but different definitions depending on the perspective.

Organizational culture is found in all organizations, without exception, regardless of their type. In schools, the concept of organizational culture is also very important.

A rather neglected concept has been that of improving organizational culture, Schein (1999) considered that the essence of organizational culture is "the deeper level of basic assumptions and beliefs that are shared by members of an organization, that operate unconsciously and that define the organization in a basic way "for granted"".

Influencing factors of organizational culture in schools

A school's culture is honed, over time, by history, context and people. The influencing factors in this sense are represented by:

1. History (school age) can influence cultural changes. Schein (1990) identified three important periods in the development of a business organization that can be transposed in schools. Thus, in the early years, the dominant values are those transmitted from the founders of the institution, the school explaining its culture, clarifying its values and building - and a unique identity that it proves among the newcomers: teachers, students, parents. Organizational culture is the connecting network on which development is supported. Around the middle of its age, the institution is fairly well integrated, but the process of growth and renewal is not completed . It is possible that, in external and internal contexts, there have been changes that have altered strengths and weaknesses. The defining aspects of culture are now integrated and taken for granted, making organizational culture increasingly implicit. Subcultures have also emerged that slow down the process of cultural awareness, so that change becomes more and more difficult. Stagnation/stability or decline are real challenges to the change process. This level is reached when the school no longer provides feedback to its environment. Dysfunctional elements emerge, but the school faces challenges launched by old assumptions. [Fink, 1999].

2. The external environment of the school organization also shapes its organizational culture. Each community formed by students, their parents present their own ideas about how a real school should be, ideas born from their own experience as students. This fact is very clear from the phrase " a real school is what I went to when I was a child " [Metz, 1991]. Different factors such as political, economic or legislative ones can also influence the organizational culture of a school. For example, education unions, as part of the institution's external environment, can influence a school's culture and/or influence the institution's focus on improvement.

3. Primary and secondary school cultures are different [Cooper, 1988]. In primary institutions the culture is influenced by care and control, hence the feeling of leaving the family when students leave primary school. The culture in the secondary school is characterized both by the size and structure of the departments, and by the academic orientation of the teachers - the difference between a science teacher and an art teacher, as well as the experience of students moving from one teacher to another and from one discipline to another.

4. The students of the institution and their social environment also influence the school culture. Thrupp believes that the social mix of the school is a determining factor in the way the institution functions, starting from the influence exerted by the interactions between the students. In principle, the students of the institution give it a special note, through the student culture. This aspect acquires an additional connotation when they reach the age of adolescence, when values and identities undergo changes. [Thrupp, 1997].

5. School culture is also provoked by social changes regardless of whether they are connected to learning, school population, management, technology or the repositioning of women in society [Dalin & Rolff, 1993]. The school must react quickly to these changes. Although culture can change as a result of changes in participants, it can also play a stabilizing role, especially for the long-lived parts of the culture. For this reason school organizational culture can seem immobile to those who follow rapid changes. Although it has both characteristics - dynamic and static - culture constantly evolves and reconstructs itself [Hopkins, Ainscow and West, 1994].

Figure 1. Influencing factors of school organizational culture, adaptation after (Hopkins, Ainscow, & West, 1994)

Changing an organizational culture generally means limited change or fundamental change. The specialist literature mentions three typologies of efforts for cultural change: revolutionary efforts aimed at deeply modifying the organizational culture; phased efforts that, through their entirety, desire a substantial reshaping of the culture; limited efforts aim changes at the level of subcultures or some components of the organizational culture.

Effective organizational culture change involves the following strategies: unfreezing the old culture and developing motivation for change; fruition of favorable moments-opportunities, changed situations or past deficiencies; establishing the clear objective of the change; maintaining continuity with the past; creating a safe psychological environment, formal and informal training of relevant teams, identifying and presenting positive role models, hiring staff, having support groups for overcoming losses or fears; creating behaviours, cultural forms, artefacts and establishing appropriate socialization tactics; promoting charismatic leaders; making a solid transition plan; the integration of the understanding and avoidance of risks and benefits in risk management, as well as the inequitable allocation of risks and/or benefits [Schein, 1999].

Structure and culture are interrelated concepts. Most efforts to improve the school are directed towards structural changes: time - for example dividing the school year into four-five periods delimited by short breaks; space- moving related departments such as science and mathematics to the same floor to encourage cooperation; roles and responsibilities - creating a change/school improvement manager position [Bush, T.G, 2014].

This aspect derives from the ease of manipulation of the structures. In order for them to make changes, more attention must be paid to the adjacent subculture. And culture can be influenced by structures. For example, if you want to increase the degree of collegiality between teachers, but the program does not allow them to meet during the day, there will be a barrier. Andy Hargreaves notes that teaching is expected to be an isolated act because "Structures of teacher isolation have their roots in schools that have been organized as egg crates since the mid-nineteenth century" [Hargreaves et al., 1996].

School improvement initiatives introduced by national decision-makers place great importance on so-called rational-empirical change strategies. These are based on the idea that schools are rational places and the people inside them adopt the proposed changes if they are shown to benefit them. From Clark and Guba's linear analysis a model of educational change emerges - "research, development and dissemination" (R, D+D) [Clark & Guba, 1965].

Figure 2. The model of the stages of educational change, adaptation after [Clark & Guba, 1965]

Schools strive to create positive culture and climate by training all members. The development of school culture is based on a set of beliefs, values and norms that are generally accepted and consciously implemented as a natural behavior that creates a bridge between school elements and stakeholders. Useful steps that the school can take to achieve a favorable culture - include the formulation of strategies, the analysis of the internal and external environment, the implementation of established strategies and monitoring or carrying out an evaluation.

In order to get a picture of the culture and climate existing in the school, the internal and external environments are analyzed. At the same time, the possibility of developing the necessary information technology is of increased relevance. SWOT analysis can be used in this

case. The vision, mission and objectives of the institution must incorporate the strategies and be understood by all stakeholders. Different behavioral habits generally derive from differences in understanding of the vision, mission or objectives. Their uniform understanding directs collective behavior toward the school's vision, mission, and goals [Cavanagh, R. F., & Dellar, G.B., 1998].

Implementation of the strategy is an activity that must be carried out by schools, related to the habit of achieving, communicating, interacting, and providing a healthy and pleasant school environment. Ensuring the school environment is linked to meeting school standards, as stipulated in the National Education Law. The buildings meet the health requirements, are properly ventilated and lit, are connected to water and sewage, have a rainwater distribution system and waste collection systems [Lubis, F. R., & Hanum, F. 2019].

Monitoring and evaluating activities can be done to determine the development of the existing system and the performance of each implementer to create an enabling school. Monitoring can be done throughout the year, while evaluations can be done monthly, semestrial, and yearly, at the end [Bower, R. J., & Scheerens, J. 1994].

Considering the previous explanation, it can be said that the learning outcomes of the students and the quality of the school depends on the organizational culture and the school climate. The latter can benefit the principals, teachers, administrative staff and students. The principal can easily manage the school, teachers easily do their work, students feel valued, safe, and parents feel accepted and involved in school activities. These are major benefits that support school success [Gruenert & Whitaker, 2015].

Discussion and conclusions

Educational institutions and different categories of organizations must focus on building and sustaining organizational cultures.

School improvement initiatives introduced by national decision-makers and beyond place great importance on so-called rational-empirical change strategies. These are based on the idea that schools are rational places and the people inside them adopt the proposed changes if they are shown to benefit them.

Just as no one person is identical to another, the organizational culture in one institution cannot be the same as another.

The public sector has mainly practiced a hierarchical culture based on rules, procedures, and stability over time, but to increase efficiency it should borrow more from the entrepreneurial organizational culture.

Limitations and future research directions

Pre-university education institutions differ from each other from several perspectives. In addition to the children's level (age) (preschool, primary, secondary, high school, professional), differences can be mentioned even between institutions at the same level. For example, a rural school is very different from an urban school. Likewise, a theoretical high school differs fundamentally from a technological one.

Beyond these aspects related to students, human resources play an essential role in creating or changing the organizational culture in schools. However, each person is unique, and hence the uniqueness of each collective in schools.

This paper provides an overview but is not specific in any way. An interesting future research direction could be the analysis of school organizational cultures by school level. It would be equally useful to analyze and compare the organizational cultures in the rural environment with those in the urban environment.

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